

THE EFFECT OF THE FEEDING PROCEDURE ON THE FOOD INTAKE OF CHICKENS

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Annotation. This scientific paper provides information that the level of consumption of the feed ration formed for chickens of different ages increases, in contrast to the level of feed consumption under the influence of the feeding order of chickens, that is, the neighborhood that provides food.

Keywords: food, feeding procedure, feed ration, consumption, hen, chicken.

In order to ensure the stability of food security in the country in recent years, special attention is paid to the development of the poultry industry, providing the population with high-quality and affordable poultry products of domestic production, the development of scientifically based norms for feeding poultry, and the development of measures aimed at controlling the composition and quality of the feed. (1)

As a result of these opportunities, the number of heads of chickens has recently increased in our country, as well as the quality indicators of the products obtained from them are improving, strengthening the feed base for poultry in further improving the efficiency of these farms. The urgent issues of today are the search for optimal indicators for increasing the level of consumption by animals, that is, chickens, of the feed formed by them, as well as their scientific justification and application in practice, effectively establishing the feeding procedure for chickens and chicks.

Based on the above, we faced the purpose of the study in different ways in order to increase the consumption of feed rations for chickens of different ages (the age of chickens in daily accounting), the order of their feeding was determined differently,

during our study, the control group and the experimental group were formed from broiler chickens "Kobb 500" .

Chickens of the experimental and control groups were bred in special cages, where the number of experimental animals in each group was 10, the level of feed consumption by chickens, how much feed fed into special feeding containers was consumed as feed, and how much was left without food, were calculated by simple calculation, weighing on special scales. During our experiment, the chickens were supplied with water based on the norm.

In the course of our research, the chickens of the experimental group were fed 8 times a day, i.e. during the 1st week after hatching, each head of chickens was fed 8 times a day, forming an average of 7-8 grams of compound feed and placing them in special cages filled with soaked feed, and in the 2nd week each head of chickens fed (1 table).

Feed consumption indicators ($m \pm m$. $n=10$)

No	Age of the chickens (weekly)	Amount of food	Food intake Control	Experiment
1	1 weekly	40.0	23.1 $\pm$ 1.12	26.4 $\pm$ 1.08
2	2 weekly	85.0	64.24 $\pm$ 0.68	71.61 $\pm$ 2.25
3	3 weekly	125.0	99.75 $\pm$ 3.05	106.48 $\pm$ 2.14
4	4 weekly	170.0	128.33 $\pm$ 3.15	129.12 $\pm$ 1.93
5	5 weekly	230.0	135.22 $\pm$ 2.74	136.91 $\pm$ 2.85

The control group was raised 1-4 times a Week, 3 times from 2-3 weeks, and from 4 weeks, all control group chickens were raised 2 times. During our observations, the feed intake rate of each head chicken is shown in Table 1 below, which lists the total amount of feed given to 1 Head of chicken per day and at the same time the total amount of feed consumed by one head of chicken.

According to the data presented in the table above, feeding chicks 8 times a day led to an increase in feed consumption by 14.28%, where, as a reason for an increase in the level of feed consumption, the more feeds in front of chickens, the more difficult its surface will be, a decrease in efficiency, in addition, according to our results. In conclusion, it can be said that during the first 1, 2 and 3 weeks of feeding broiler chicks in the meat direction, it is possible to achieve an increase in the level of feed consumption of chicks in exchange for a relative increase in the feeding skill, and as a result, it can also increase the daily growth indicators of chicks.

References:

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